

Cyclopentanone-2-Carboxyanilide as a Gravimetric Reagent for Mercury(II)

NIRMAL KUSUM CHAUDHURI** and JYOTIRMOY DAS*

Chemistry Department, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713101

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Mercury (II) in quantities 25-40 mg has been determined gravimetrically by precipitating it as the cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide complex, $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$, containing 33.18% of the metal. The precipitation is quantitative in the pH-range, 5.5-8.6. The complex can be weighed directly if it is dried below 105° for half an hour and then at 110° - 115° . Mercury (II) has also been separated quantitatively from Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , and Al^{3+} . In these separations citric acid-sodium citrate buffer acts as masking agent. The relative standard deviation is $\pm 0.32\%$.

THE electronic configuration of mercury(II) is favourable for coordination with highly polarising ligands containing elements like nitrogen and sulphur. However, under well defined conditions oxygenated ligands may also form stable chelates with this metal ion and when this is feasible separation of mercury(II) from other metal ions commonly associated with it, can be achieved easily.

Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide, a reagent first introduced for gravimetric, titrimetric and spectrophotometric determination of beryllium¹ has now been used in the estimation of mercury(II) and its separation from a number of metal ions. It is very likely that the complex has the structure

Though the nitrogen atom is also situated in a position for coordination, the resonating structures of the amide group suggest the donation through oxygen because of its higher electronegativity than nitrogen². Moreover from the studies of the beryllium and copper chelates of various substituted acetoacetamides, Harries³ as well as Kettrup and Riepe⁴ have concluded that two oxygen atoms are involved in the bonding

Experimental

Cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide solution : The reagent was prepared by the condensation of aniline with ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate⁵. This ester was obtained from adipic ester by Dieckman condensation.

Fresh solutions of the reagent (0.35-0.45g) in aqueous ethanol (5 ml) were prepared before use. The dissociation constant of the reagent was determined by pH titration and the pKa value obtained was 10.14.

Mercury(II) solution : Pure mercury(II) nitrate (E. Merck) was dissolved in water containing a little nitric acid, and the metal content was determined gravimetrically^{6,7}.

Buffer solution : A citric acid-sodium citrate buffer of pH 6.5 was used.

Apparatus : A battery operated bench model Cambridge pH-meter was used to measure the pH-values. For the thermal decomposition studies, a penrecording Aminco Thermoanalyser was used.

Procedure for mercury : An aliquot of the mercury (II) nitrate solution containing 25-40 mg of the metal was treated with 1% sodium hydroxide solution to neutralise the free nitric acid present taking care that no mercury oxide was formed. If any of this was formed, it was dissolved by the addition of minimum amount of nitric acid. The solution was diluted to 150 ml and heated to about 50° . The reagent solution was then added dropwise with stirring and the pH was adjusted to

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MERCURY(II)

Hg taken, (mg)	Wt. of complex (mg)	Hg found (mg)	Rel. Error (%)
25.1	75.7	25.1	nil
	75.3	25.0	-0.4
35.0	105.4	35.0	nil
	105.0	34.8	-0.57
40.0	121.2	40.2	+0.50
	120.6	40.0	nil

** Present Address : Radiochemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Energy Centre, Trombay, Bombay.

5.5-8.6 with sodium hydroxide (1-2N), added cautiously. A white precipitate was formed when the solution was allowed to cool below 35° and this settled down nicely on keeping the mixture for 30-45 min. at room temperature with occasional stirring. The complex was filtered, washed with water and allowed to dry below 105° for 30 min. and then at 110°-115° for 15 min. The complex, $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ containing 33.18% of the metal was weighed. The results are given in Table 1.

Procedure in the presence of diverse ions : About 10 ml of the citrate-buffer of pH 6.5 was added to the mixture of mercury(II) and the foreign ions. After heating this to 50°-60° the reagent (0.45 g in 5 ml aqueous ethanol) was added and the pH was raised to 7.0 with the dropwise addition of sodium hydroxide solution (2%). The mixture was cooled to room temperature and allowed to stand for about 30 min. The precipitate was filtered, washed first with water containing a little citrate (pH 6.0) and finally with water. The process of drying was the same as above.

Results and Discussion

Properties and composition of the complex : The mercury(II)-cyclopentanone-2-carboxyanilide complex was obtained as a colourless precipitate, but blackened overnight when it was left in wet condition. The dried complex was stable for days. The complex was partly soluble in aqueous ethanol at elevated temperatures. When the wet complex was subjected to drying at 110° or above it turned light grey, probably due to hydrolysis and consequently there was a slight loss in weight. But no such change was observed on drying at about 100°.

The complex was analysed for nitrogen using Kjeldahl's method. The experimental value (4.55%, 4.58%) indicated that the bis-complex, $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2$ was obtained which should contain 4.63% of nitrogen.

Thermal decomposition of the complex : A known weight of the oven-dried (105°) sample was subjected to thermogravimetric analysis. The thermal decomposition curve indicated that the complex, HgR_2 ($\text{R}=\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}$) was stable upto 170°, when it started decomposing. Around 360° there was another sharp loss in weight (about 34%).

Optimum pH and reagent concentration : The pH range for quantitative precipitation was found to be 5.5-8.6, and a five-fold excess of the reagent was necessary.

Effect of Sequestering agents : The presence of ethylenediamine tetraacetate or nitrilotriacetate completely prevented the precipitation of mercury while it was only partial in the presence of tartrate or fluoride.

However, citrate ions did not show any adverse effect. Thus citrate buffer was used for adjustment of pH as well as to mask other metal ions.

Effect of diverse ions : Mercury (II) (35 mg) was separated from 50 mg of copper(II), cadmium(II), bismuth(III), zinc(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), iron(III) or aluminium(III) with an average relative error of $\pm 0.24\%$.

Standard deviation : The relative standard deviation in the determination of mercury (II) by the given method was $\pm 0.32\%$ in 20 determinations.

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